

Effects And Association Of Skipping Breakfast On Academic Performance In Medical Students

Lubna Riaz, Muhammad Noman Rashid, Fareeha Butt, Asshad Ahmed Siddiqui, Hina Riaz, Riaz Ahmed Shahid

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: October 04, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: May 05, 2022</p> <p>Keywords : Academic performance, Breakfast, Effects, Medical students, Skipping.</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6519241</p>	<p>Background: Breakfast is considered as a most important meal of the day for providing energy to body and to brain for improved learning. The habits of skipping breakfast may affect performance mentally and physically whole day. The objective of this study is to evaluate the effects and association of skipping breakfast on academic performance in medical students.</p> <p>Subjects and methods: This cross-sectional descriptive study was conducted in medical students of Dow University of Health Sciences (DUHS) and Lyari Medical College Karachi. From March to September in 2019. After approval of research by the Lyari Medical College Karachi ethics review committee. Total 440 students were enrolled after taking consent. Students having history of gastro intestinal diseases and pregnancy were excluded. Data collection was done by using a self-administered close ended questionnaire. The first part of the questionnaire asked about Cumulative Grade Point Average (CGPA) up to the last semester examination results. The second part of the questionnaire enquired the breakfast consumption pattern. Whereas the last part asked about the respondent's perception on their cognitive aspects and general physical aspects with regards to breakfast consumption. The data was analyzed using SPSS version 22. Chi square test was used to analyze the qualitative data.</p> <p>Results: The CGPA of breakfast skippers was <3.00, whereas breakfast takers had good grade points.</p> <p>Conclusion: It was concluded that skipping breakfast have negative impacts on health and academic performance of the medical students.</p>

Introduction

Breakfast is considered as a most important meal of the day for providing energy to body and brain for improved learning. The habits of skipping breakfast may affect performance mentally and physically the whole day. Breakfast is often regarded as a most critical meal of the day, as its nutritional significance determines multiple aspects of physical and mental wellbeing of an individual's body. Taking breakfast lowers raised levels of cortisol (stress hormone), which surges early in the morning. Regular breakfast consumption provides instant energy source and restores glucose level in the blood.¹ Regular breakfast intake is regarded as a marker of health, which includes consumption of nutrients (micro and macronutrients) daily. It provides higher concentration of nutrients like carbohydrates, proteins, dietary fibers, iron, calcium and vitamin C and lowers concentration of fats.² Regular breakfast consumption exerts positive effects on physical activities (energy system), stress, cognitive performance or concentration levels or memory, special senses (visual, hearing and vestibular system).³ Skipping breakfast leads to failure of replenishment of energy sources thus low levels of glucose can impact on performing mental tasks and ability to concentrate.⁴ Its nutritional contribution cannot be met by any other meal of the day.⁵ Breakfast consumption is positively associated with children's cognitive performance.⁶ The practices of intake of breakfast are associated with many factors like cultural, educational, physiological and socioeconomic status in society or behaviors. Irregular breakfast consumption habits are associated with easy fatigability, altered memory or cognitive performance, increased adiposity, that will lead to development of the cardiovascular or cardio-metabolic diseases, and diabetes mellitus due to increased insulin resistance.⁷ The detrimental effects of skipping breakfast on cognition are more pronounced in malnourished children than well nourished.^{8,9} The adverse effects of skipping breakfast are significant on school attendance, memory, academic performance and psychosocial function in children as well as in young people.¹⁰ In European countries the prevalence of skipping breakfast in students varies from 10-30% , while in China and India its prevalence varies from 40-45% respectively.^{11,12} The positive outcomes of breakfast consumption in university students are improved organizational attendance, nutrient intake, fitness and university performance.¹³ Healthy life style of medical students is mainly dependent on taking healthy and regular breakfast as compared to skippers and unhealthy

life style is dependent mainly on using fast food, junk foods, sedentary life style, smoking, and tea.¹⁴ For this study was developed in order to collect data on effects and association of skipping breakfast on medical students. As these medical students should understand about the importance of taking breakfast and development of the healthy lifestyle by adopting healthy eating patterns in breakfast, for future practicing doctor and considered as the promoters of health in community. Academic Performance was evaluated by cumulative grade point average (CGPA). Student's CGPA used was based on their CGPA up to the last semester of the current year of study. Good grade point was categorized as CGPA more than 3 whereas poor grade points less than 3.¹⁵ Rationale of this study focused on effects of skipping breakfast on academic performance of medical students in learning of medical education. Objective was to find out the effects and association of skipping breakfast on academic performance in medical students.

Methodology

This is a descriptive cross-sectional study, conducted among the MBBS students of Dow University of Health Sciences and Lyari Medical College Karachi. The sample size was calculated by Raosoft was figured to be 440 with alpha level 5% and confidence level 95%. Non probability convenience sampling was used. Total of 440 medical students with age ranges from 18-24 years were enrolled after taking informed consent. Approval of research was obtained from the department of postgraduate Medical Education, Training, Research & Ethics of SMBBMCL & Ethical and scientific review board (ESRB). All the included medical students of the research were informed about the topic and its significance. The duration of study was six months, from March to September 2019. Medical students from second year to final year studying at DUHS and its constituent medical colleges were included after obtaining consent. Students having history of diabetes mellitus (DM) or any hormonal disorders or metabolic disorders, lactose intolerance, anorexia nervosa, bulimia nervosa, pregnancy and food allergies were excluded. Data was collected from the institutes with the help of pre-tested questionnaire by using a self-administered close ended questionnaire. The first part of the questionnaire asked about Cumulative Grade Point Average (CGPA) up to the last semester examination results. The second part of the questionnaire enquired the breakfast consumption pattern. Whereas the last part asked about the respondents perception on their cognitive aspects and general physical aspects with regards to breakfast consumption. The data were analyzed by SPSS (Statistical package of social sciences) version 22.0 applied. Means and standard (\pm) deviations of quantitative variables while frequencies and percentages (%) and Pearson Chi Square test (χ^2) was used to analyze the qualitative data. Chi-square test (χ^2) was applied to find out association amongst dependent and independent variables that is Cumulative Grade Point Average (CGPA) and breakfast consumption at a 95% level of significance. The $p < 0.05$ was considered as a statistically significant in study results.

RESULTS

The 440 MBBS students from second year to final year of Dow medical college of Dow University (DMC & DUHS) and Lyari Medical College (SMBBMCL) participated in the study. There were 72 (16.36%) males and 368 (83.6%) females. The first part of the results determined breakfast skippers from all four years. Table- 1 reports the number and percentage of Breakfast taker & Breakfast skipper medical students in different classes; i-e Second year [112 (88%) & 28 (12%)], Third year [86(86%) & 14(14%)], Fourth year [81(81%) & 19(19%)] and Final year [83(83%) & 17(17%)]. Table-2 summarizes the groups' statistics comparison of CGPA between Breakfast taker and Breakfast skippers. In medical students from second year to final year MBBS students of MBBS have significant difference was observed ($p < 0.05$), and second year students showed significant ($p < 0.05$) differences. While third year, fourth year and final year did not showed significant ($p > 0.05$) differences among students. The mean CGPA of the breakfast takers was 3.1 with p -value < 0.01 (Table No.2). The self-reported effects of breakfast consumption in Table-3 reports, that the majority of students perceived enhancement in their cognition and learning capabilities (70.6%) being, physically active throughout the day (68.6%), and participating actively in interactive session (51.1%). Table-3, depicts that mostly students denied (74.1%) about improvement in GPA after taking regular breakfast. It was also observed by mostly students that they easily fatigued even after doing small activities after skipping breakfast routinely, and also causes headache (51.7%), dizziness (51.7%), and disturbed memory (56.4%) (Table 4).

Table 1. Breakfast Taker and Breakfast Skipper of Medical Students

Study Years	Breakfast taker %	Breakfast skipper %
2 nd Year (n=140)	88	12
3 rd Year (n=100)	86	14
4 th year (n=100)	81	19
5 th Year (n=100)	83	17

Table 2. Groups Statistics Comparison between Breakfast taker and Breakfast Skippers of Cumulative Grade Point Average (CGPA).

Year of Study	Breakfast taker Mean± SD	Breakfast skipper Mean± SD	T- value	p- value
2 nd Year (n=140)	3.43±0.39	3.14±0.48	2.98	<0.01
3 rd Year (n=100)	3.14±0.37	2.94±0.49	2.18	0.03*
4 th year (n=100)	3.12±0.37	3.02±0.31	1.30	0.19
5 th Year (n=100)	2.96±0.35	2.90±0.31	0.72	0.46

*p<0.05 was considered significant

Table 3. Self-Reported Effects of Breakfast Consumption.

Questions	Yes N (%)	No N (%)
Do you feel taking breakfast enhances your cognition and learning capabilities?	311(70.6%)	129(29.36%)

Do you notice taking breakfast improves your GPA?	118(36.8%)	322(74.1%)
Do you think breakfast keeps you physically active throughout the day?	302(68.6%)	138(31.3%)
After skipping breakfast do you easily fatigued even after doing small activities?	225(51.1%)	215(48.8%)
Can you participate actively in interactive session?	225(51.1%)	215(48.8%)

Table 4. Self-Reported Effects of Skipping Breakfast

Variables	Yes N (%)	No N (%)
Have you ever feel dizzy during university hours?	213(48.3%)	227(51.7%)
Do you feel headache while in university?	213(48.3%)	227(51.7%)
Can you participate actively in interactive session?	317(72%)	123(28%)
Can you concentrate on studies (either in lectures, ward or in library)?	334(75.8%)	106(24.2%)
Do you frequently lose your attention during lecture or wards?	253(57.5%)	187(42.5%)
Do you feel skipping breakfast adversely affect your memory?	192(43.6%)	248(56.4%)
Do you feel low, dull or tired in lectures/ward in the morning?	235(53.3%)	205(46.7%)
Have you ever experienced nausea/hunger pains?	257(58.3)	183(41.7)
Do you feel mostly stressed throughout your day?	227(51.7)	213(48.3)

DISCUSSION

The objective of this study was to evaluate the association between effects of skipping breakfast on academic performance in medical students of Karachi. In this descriptive study students were included from different classes of constituent medical colleges of Dow University (DMC & DUHS). The total number of medical students participated were 440 and among the females were 368 (83.6%) in this study. It is similar to other studies, in which female gender participated in higher percentage¹⁶⁻¹⁸. Skipping breakfast is negatively associated with Cumulative Grade point average (CGPA) of the medical students in this observational study and self-reported effects of the breakfast consumption on the learning capability were pronounced. However many skippers didn't report that skipping breakfast affected their learning capability, but their CGPA was less than that of breakfast takers. The effects on physical aspects were reported by both skippers and takers as coherent with breakfast consumption¹⁹. The positive effect of regular breakfast (in terms of frequency and quality) in children and adolescents has been demonstrated by many studies. The academic performance was evaluated by using standardized achievement tests and formal school grades⁴. Another study demonstrated similar association between academic performance and breakfast consumption. The adolescents who frequently took breakfast had better academic performance than who took breakfast infrequently. The school grades were considered in this study¹⁹ and the present study has similar results. Another cross-sectional study reported that breakfast takers of 10th grade students had better school grades than that of breakfast skippers. It also addressed that the implications of skipping breakfast on mental distress and academic performance are stronger for boys than girls.²⁰ This study is consistent with results of present study regarding mental distress and academic performance (Table No.4). Another cross-sectional study from University Kebangsaan Malaysia reported that academic performance in terms of CGPA was associated with quantity of breakfast in terms of energy and macronutrient contents.¹⁵ Current study results are in agreement with previous study regarding Cumulative Grade point average (CGPA) but caloric parameters were not enquired in the study. Hence, it is recommended that other studies should be carried out to elaborate association between skipping breakfast and academic performance including caloric aspect of breakfast. Also Standard achievement test should be employed to assess breakfast consumption effects on cognition and academic achievement in medical students.

CONCLUSION

Most of the medical students are breakfast takers and have found association between skipping breakfast and academic performance with having detrimental effects on CGPA of medical students. Also there has been association between breakfast consumption pattern and other aspects of learning capabilities.

Conflict of interest: The authors declared no conflict of interest exist.

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Author Information

Lubna Riaz

Assistant Professor, Department of Forensic Medicine, Dow University of Health Sciences Karachi

Muhammad Noman Rashid

Assistant Professor, Department of Physiology, Director Postgraduate Medical Education, Research and Ethics Department, Shaheed Mohtarma Benazir Bhutto Medical College, Dow University of Health Sciences, Karachi

Fareeha Butt

Assistant Professor, Department of Physiology, Dow University of Health Sciences Karachi

Asshad Ahmed Siddiqui

Assistant Professor, Department of Anatomy, Dow University of Health Sciences Karachi

Hina Riaz

Assistant Professor, Department of Physiology, Dow University of Health Sciences Karachi

Riaz Ahmed Shahid

Associate Professor, Department of Physiology, Dow University of Health Sciences Karachi
